

Subphrenic Abscess as an Atypical Presentation of Peptic Ulcer Perforation

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Abstract

Subphrenic abscesses are rare but serious complications of gastrointestinal perforations, often presenting with nonspecific symptoms that delay diagnosis. Posteriorly located or small duodeno-gastric ulcers may be contained by adjacent tissues, leading to localized abscess formation rather than diffuse peritonitis. CT imaging is key to diagnosis, while percutaneous drainage is the preferred treatment but the surgery may be needed to treat the cause. Identifying and managing the underlying cause, such as a small perforated ulcer, is essential.

Introduction

Subphrenic abscesses are collections of pus located beneath the diaphragm, often resulting from intra-abdominal infections or postoperative complications. While they are relatively rare, their occurrence can signify underlying pathologies, such as gastrointestinal perforations. This article discusses a case where a subphrenic abscess unveiled a perforated gastric ulcer, highlighting the diagnostic challenges and management strategies involved.

Case Report

A 64-year-old female patient, known to have hypertension managed with diuretics and under investigation for renal insufficiency, was admitted to the emergency department for epigastric pain evolving over the past 20 days, without any associated symptoms. The condition developed in an afebrile context with preserved general condition.

On clinical examination, the patient was conscious and stable hemodynamically and respiratorily. Abdominal examination revealed painful hepatomegaly, with the liver span measuring 16 cm.

More Information

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An abdominal X-ray without preparation did not show any pneumoperitoneum but revealed elevation of the left diaphragmatic dome.

Figure 1: Abdominal X-Ray without Preparation Showing the Left Diaphragmatic Dome Elevation

An abdominal CT scan showed an enlarged liver (19 cm) and a large subcapsular lesion in segments II and III, measuring 177 x 110 mm, with liquid density, no

detectable septations or wall, and no enhancement after contrast injection. There was no pneumoperitoneum or pleural effusion.

Figure 2: CT Scan Image Showing the Hepatic cyst

Biological tests revealed hyperleukocytosis at 11,000/mm³ and a C-reactive protein (CRP) level of 199 mg/L. The patient was started on dual antibiotic therapy with ceftriaxone 2 g/day and metronidazole 500 mg three times daily. An ultrasound-guided drainage was performed, yielding 200 cc of pus on the first day and 50 cc on the second day. Follow-up labs showed normalization of the white blood cell count (5,100/mm³) and a decrease in CRP to 66 mg/L. A follow-up ultrasound showed persistence of the collection with no significant reduction in size, leading to the indication for surgical drainage. A laparoscopic approach was initially performed. Exploration revealed a 250 cc purulent subhepatic collection, which was evacuated. However, the presence of multiple hepatogastric and gastroepiploic adhesions made dissection at that level hazardous, prompting conversion to laparotomy.

Figure 4: Laparoscopic Intraoperative Image Showing Pus Drainage through Adhesions in the Supramesocolic Space

Figure 3: Peroperative Laparoscopic View Showing Adhesions between the Greater Omentum and the Anterior Abdominal Wall, Obstructing Access to the Supramesocolic Compartment

Figure 5: Laparoscopic Intraoperative Image Showing the Purulent Cavity and Surrounding the Hepatogastric and Gastroepiploic Adhesions

A midline incision was made. After careful dissection of the adhesions, exploration revealed a purulent collection of 700 cc originating from a 2 cm gastric perforation located in the prepyloric region. Peritoneal lavage was performed, the perforation was closed with simple sutures, and drainage was placed in the subhepatic and inter-hepato-diaphragmatic spaces using a Salem tube.

Figure 6: Intraoperative Image after Conversion to Laparotomy Revealing a Prepyloric Gastric Perforation

Postoperative recovery was uneventful: bowel transit resumed on postoperative day 2, and oral intake was reintroduced on day 3 without complications. The drains, which produced only serous fluid, were removed on postoperative day 4. The patient was discharged on postoperative day 5.

Discussion

Subphrenic abscesses remain a relatively uncommon yet potentially life-threatening consequence of intra-abdominal infections, particularly when associated with gastrointestinal perforations. The diagnosis can be delayed due to the non-specificity of symptoms and the deep anatomical location of the abscess, especially in the posterior subphrenic space [1].

Perforated duodeno-gastric ulcers are a well-known cause of peritonitis; however, in certain cases—especially those with a posteriorly located perforation—the spillage of gastric contents may localize and evolve into a walled-off collection, leading to subphrenic abscess formation rather than generalized peritonitis [2]. This phenomenon is more likely when the omentum or adjacent organs help contain the perforation [3]. Also, the patient may have a very small perforation precluding peritoneal exposure of intestinal contents or may have an ulcer opening into an abscess cavity that may develop due to an

incomplete local peritoneal immune response to localize the perforation [1].

Diagnostic imaging is paramount in identifying subphrenic collections. CT scanning with contrast enhancement is the most sensitive modality, revealing both the abscess and any evidence of free air or associated gastrointestinal perforation [4].

Once a subphrenic abscess is diagnosed, prompt percutaneous or surgical drainage is essential. Percutaneous drainage, under CT or ultrasound guidance, remains the preferred method due to its minimally invasive nature and high success rates [5].

Identifying and addressing the primary cause of the abscess is crucial for preventing recurrence. In patients with duodeno-gastric ulcer perforations, an upper gastrointestinal contrast series can aid in pinpointing the leak site, particularly when endoscopy is contraindicated due to inflammation or high risk of perforation exacerbation [6]. Proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) are essential in managing peptic ulcer disease and aiding mucosal healing, while adjuncts such as octreotide may help reduce gastrointestinal secretions in certain contexts [1,6].

The use of an anti-inflammatory medication, painkiller like methadone, or recreational drug may blunt the symptoms of acute abdomen. Opioid use may delay symptom recognition due to altered pain perception and decreased gastrointestinal motility, potentially contributing to delayed diagnosis and treatment [7,1].

Conclusion

This case highlights the importance of maintaining a high index of suspicion for hidden gastrointestinal sources in atypical presentations of subphrenic abscesses.

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